
**THE ORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF AN
INNOVATIVE AND INTEGRATED APPROACH TO PRIMARY EDUCATION**

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Abstract

This article discusses the use of innovation and integration activities in the educational system and the scientific-theoretical significance of these activities in primary education.

Key words

Educational system, primary education, innovation, integration, Jan Amos Comenius, D. Locke.

As the President emphasized, "If children do not learn to think freely, it is inevitable that the effectiveness of the given education will be low." Of course, knowledge is needed. But knowledge is on its way. And independent thinking is a great asset. The main task of the teacher is to develop the skills of independent thinking in students. To implement the law "On Education" and the national program of personnel training, training of highly educated teachers who can meet the requirements of the times remains one of the important tasks of continuous education. Equipping students with the knowledge provided for in the state educational standards is important in many ways, the correct organization of the educational process, especially the introduction of integrated education.

The teacher is looking for the ways, methods and methods, teaching forms, methods and situations that are convenient for him and the students to activate the students, based on the modern pedagogical technologies, the effectiveness of the educational process is integrated. develops through lim. He tries to achieve high quality and efficiency of the educational process by teaching students to interdisciplinarity, independent thinking. The main goal of integrating education is to lay the foundations of a good perception of nature and society in elementary school and to form one's attitude to the laws of their development. That is why it is important for a junior high school student to see the subject or event from several angles: logically and emotionally, in a work of art, and in a scientific and popular

article, from the point of view of a biologist, wordsmith, artist, musician, etc. The results of integrated lessons are reflected in the development of creative subjects of teachers.

Scientists say that integration accelerates the formation of the student's worldview. Integrated teaching acquires knowledge, skills and competences through independent work, formation of creative abilities, active participation in classes. The content of a lesson and the structure of its delivery are taken as the basis of integration, and we can involve other subjects to enrich it. Integration, as an educational goal, should not provide knowledge showing the interdependence of separate parts of the world system, but should teach the child in the first steps to imagine a whole world in which all its elements are interconnected. This goal should be implemented in primary school classes.

The main goal of the integration of education is to form a better perception of nature and society in primary school and to direct one's attitude to the laws of their development. That is why it is important for a junior high school student to see the subject or events from several angles. Mastering the basic subjects and teaching intra-subject and inter-subject connections in understanding the laws of things in the world is the methodological basis of the approach to the integration of education. This can be achieved by returning many times to the concepts of different lessons, deepening and enriching them, identifying important signs that are understandable to this age. Thus, any lesson, which has a well-formed, structured and structured structure, includes a group of concepts related to this educational subject, can be taken as a basis for integration.

However, the results of the analysis of concepts related to other subjects and other educational subjects are included in the integrated lesson. For example, such concepts as "winter", "cold", "storm" are considered in the lessons of reading, Russian language, science, music, visual arts. The analysis of concepts is integrated in the lessons that refer to the knowledge acquired in other educational lessons. The lesson will be creative and free, but it will have a coherent, logical sequence, a unique transition methodology. Many concepts in elementary school, which lay the foundations of general education, are common to science, Russian language, music, visual arts, etc. Currently, it is necessary to develop and test an integrated system of lessons, which is a psychological and methodological basis for establishing connections between common concepts for a number of educational subjects. At the same time, interdisciplinary relations should be taught at the level of the curriculum and provided with the necessary teaching tools.

Integrated lessons are an interactive educational system that explores the secrets of creating visual skills based on the deepening and expansion of integrative knowledge. Visual education system is built on the basis of various types, forms, methods, objects.

The goals and objectives of the integration course are described in the school natural-scientific education system. Methods and means of integration in the integrated (demonstration) network of knowledge: depending on the amount of time at the place of teaching in the educational plan, the time for full mastery of this course, the level of mastery of students is multi-purpose and color- characterized by color. The creation of appropriate mental excitement for students while studying each educational subject greatly helps the mastering of this material, it helps to remember it quickly, emotional awareness, and the growth of thinking ability, leads to the development of speech and imagination. Formation of different types of thinking skills in primary school students is the basis of integration. Establishing intra-subject and inter-subject connections in mastering the basic subjects and understanding the laws of things in the world is the methodological basis of the approach to the integration of education. This can be achieved by returning many times to the concepts of different lessons, deepening and enriching them, identifying important signs that are understandable to this age. Thus, any lesson that includes a group of concepts related to this educational subject can be taken as a basis for integration.

It is necessary to take into account the presence of positive and negative factors in the integration of primary education. These factors determine the methods of integration. Dispersion of subjects taught in schools creates a one-view (fragmentary) worldview in a school graduate. Dispersed teaching of general education subjects at school, not teaching them in an integral relationship with each other, hinders the students' full knowledge and understanding of the whole being, causing difficulties for the students. shoots According to our scientists, integration is one of the didactic principles and takes a leading place among them. Such a concept creates the need to once again consider the issue of integration in the educational system, the issue of interdisciplinarity and interdependence. Integration into the education system is one of the main tools for solving educational and educational tasks between the school and the community. Integrated lessons teach children to naturally understand the unity of their worldview, the coherence of events.

Integration is the convergence and connection of disciplines during the differentiation process. The process of integration is the stage of connecting the

communication between disciplines in a new, high quality, and manifests itself in a high way. It should be noted that the foundations of the integration process are based on folk pedagogy and scientific pedagogy. Integration is interdisciplinary. The foundations of interdisciplinarity emerged from the need to show and explain nature in its entirety in textbooks. The great didactic Jan Amos Comenius said: "Everything related to each other should be studied as such." Later, many pedagogues approached the idea of interdisciplinarity and contributed to its development and generalization. According to the idea of D. Locke: "In determining the content of education, one subject should be supplemented with elements and facts of other subjects." Pestalossi points out that it is even dangerous for one science to distance itself from another. Bulgarian scientists have created an integrated course for 10-12-year-old children, including natural-scientific knowledge. In the senior classes of US high schools, the science of "Earth Studies" is included, which includes physics, chemistry, geography, geology, crystallography, soil science, poletology, and the like. In Czechoslovakia, the same generalizing and integrated "Civic Education" is included. " course is included in senior classes.

In primary education, the role of the integrating link is performed by the teacher himself. It teaches children arithmetic, writing, nature and many basic concepts. He does this to the best of his ability. It is desirable to see integration in primary education on the basis of combining subjects that are relatively close to each other. At the next stages of education, he tries to combine the boundaries of the main subjects. It is necessary to take into account the presence of positive and negative factors in the integration of primary education. These factors determine the methods of integration. Y.M. Kolegin and O.L. Aleksenko point out the negative factors of integration: the limited number of educational subjects - the content of the large amount of acquired knowledge can be supplemented by reflecting the real view of the world, the interdependence of its parts. The need to develop very important reading, writing and numeracy skills. These things seem like they require disciplined teaching. But the traditional experience of teaching reading and mathematics also suggests broad integration possibilities. In this case, reading as a science includes not only literary texts, but also materials on history and natural science. Includes mathematics, arithmetic, algebraic and geometric materials. Such integration does not destroy the formation of important skills, but rather guarantees their formation.

In conclusion, we can say that there is integration, that is, interdiscipline coherence and connection. Because the goal of each subject is to develop children's

speech, moral education, ecological education, and aesthetic education, etc., are reflected in all subjects.

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